

DEVELOPING A FRAMEWORK TO MEASURE SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

Otakhonova Shakhnozabonu Shukhratjon qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

The Faculty of English Philology

shaxnozabonuotaxonova@gmail.com

***Abstract.** Developing a system to examine sociolinguistic competence in primary school students is a pressing issue today. This article explores on the importance of sociolinguistic competence, the challenges of its assessment, the evaluation system, strategies for implementing the system, and the benefits of the system in enhancing the sociolinguistic abilities of primary school learners. The study demonstrates how this system provides a more precise and detailed analysis of student's phonological development such as improving their pronunciation and become more effective in communication. Furthermore, it highlights new evaluation methods, including interactive techniques and the use of technology, are crucial for strengthening student's phonological skills.*

***Keywords.** Cognitive development, life skill, educational system, sociolinguistic competence, primary school, language assessment, cultural norms.*

Introduction. During the current globalization, being able to use the language effectively in various social situations plays an important role, especially for young students. Sociolinguistic competence - the ability to use language in accordance with social and cultural norms plays an important role in children's communication and adaptation to society. However, measuring these skills in primary school children remains a difficult task. The development of a system for analyzing sociolinguistic competence is useful in identifying the strengths and weaknesses of students and in supporting their growth. This article discusses the importance of such a system, its main components and its impact on the education system.

Main Text. Sociolinguistic competence is not only about knowing the rules of language, but also understanding cultural norms and social contexts, as well as

adapting language to the situation. For primary school students, these skills are essential for effective communication and social interaction. In multicultural and multilingual societies, developing these skills helps children adapt to various social situations and enhances their ability to interact successfully. And assessing is complex, as it involves a combination of non-linguistic elements. Traditional language measurement systems often focus on grammar and vocabulary but do not consider the ability to use language adapted to social situations. Additionally, it is necessary to consider the cognitive and social development stages of children. There are several methods for gauging sociolinguistic competence in primary school students. Firstly, tests and exercises are used to measure students' understanding of cultural norms and values, or role-playing activities, group tasks, or situations to assess how they adapt language to social contexts. Observation tools are used to examine verbal and non-verbal communication during peer interactions or group activities. Finally, simple questionnaires or interviews are used to understand students' attitudes toward their language choices. In summary, an effective monitoring system is useful in identifying students' communication skills and helps teachers adapt their teaching methods. This system enables students to develop life skills such as empathy, adaptability, and cultural sensitivity, which prepares them for future social and professional activities.

Conclusion. Sociolinguistic competence is very important for primary school students because it allows them to communicate correctly and effectively in various social situations. This, in turn, ensures their social adaptability and success in society. Developing a system for assessing sociolinguistic competence is essential to improving the learning process and supporting students' development. By addressing challenges in the measurement process and ensuring cultural sensitivity, teachers can help students not only learn the language but also understand how to apply it in different cultural contexts. This will prepare students

for future success, as they will develop the ability to use language correctly in various cultural and social contexts.

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